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Verbundwerkstoffe

Modified Curing Cycles and Accompanying Polymer and Adhesion Changes in Fiber Metal Laminates

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Chapter

1. Motivation
2. State of the art
3. Materials and methods
4. Modified curing cycle results
5. Adhesion between epoxy and metal sheets
6. Alternative approach
7. Conclusion & outlook

Fiber-metal laminates (FML) can improve:

- Damage tolerance
- Fatigue performance
 - Especially if carbon fibers are used
- Bearing strength
 - Especially if steel sheets are used

Problems associated with FML:

- Corrosion
- Surface treatment and adhesion
- Thermal residual stresses induced during the thermal cycle of polymer cure or melting

Conventional curing cycle:

$\epsilon_{th, Metal.} > 0$

$\epsilon_{th, CFRP.} \sim 0$

The modified curing cycle → lower $\Delta\vartheta$ between curing and operation :

Increased fatigue life

→ Solidification at a lower temperature

The modified curing cycle → lower $\Delta\vartheta$ between curing and operation :

$$\varepsilon_{th,CFRP} = 0$$

Further increase in fatigue life?

→ Solidification at the lowest temperature possible.

Effect of cure on fatigue crack resistance

→ Decreased fatigue crack propagation rate by increased curing temperature (identical curing time)

Effect of cure on adhesion (lap shear strength)

[Kotynia.2017]

→ Curing cycle affects the resulting lap shear strength

- Polymer
SR 1660 / SD 7820
- Carbon fiber non-crimp fabric
- Stainless spring steel
1.4310 t ~ 0.1-0.3 mm

RTM process choices:

A. Non-stationary

Cold tooling and heating ramp → good impregnation but maximum heating rate will define curing temperature, i.e. residual stresses

B. Isothermal

Preheated tooling and slightly heated resin → resin takes on tooling temperature immediately

Imperfect impregnation, due to maximized curing temperature for isothermal process (B)

Race tracking around the metal sheets

B. Isothermal process

Definition:

- Low temperature cure: 48h@35°C + Post-cure
- High temperature cure: 3h@90°C

QC of manufactured plates

- No race tracking evident
- Fully impregnated at 90°C

Seemingly no adhesion possible with various surface treatments

Lap shear specimens produced by adhesively connecting metal to metal possible, however lap shear strength depends on the curing and post-curing cycle

Conclusion: Thermal stresses during the post-cure treatment might exceed the bond strength.

Countermeasures:

- Reduced thickness of the metal sheets (0.3 mm \rightarrow 0.12 mm)
- Suitable surface treatment (DLR Braunschweig / Germany)
- Slow heating rate during post-cure ramp

Investigation of adhesive strength in a conventional lap shear setting so far unsuccessful from a testing point of view but sufficient adhesive strength was achieved across at all post-curing stages

Result: Yielding of the metal sheets before bond failure for a sufficiently large overlap

Effect of cure on fatigue crack resistance and fracture toughness

Mechanical pre-strain

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{th}(\theta) + \Delta\varepsilon_{el}$$

Strategy:

What if we could adjust the elongation of the carbon fibers to the thermal expansion of the metal sheets by applying a mechanical strain before and during cure?

Mechanical pre-strain of the carbon fibers will be released during cool down of the high temperature cured laminate

Impregnation

Ends were impregnated
and cured in preliminary
step

CF pre-stressed

Cured with elongated CF

Thermal residual stresses

High temperature cure with mechanically strained CFRP during cure

Force sensor

Clamping width
150 mm

Lifting cushion

Sandwich panel

Pre-tensioned CFRP

Heating blankets

→ Preparation of plates with $\sim 400 \times 150 \text{ mm}^2$ possible

Current working hypothesis:

Adhesion of the metal sheets develops as a function of post curing treatment and can become critical if:

- The interface needs to transfer high shear loads, e.g. as a result of thermal stresses during post-curing
- Can be different as a result of the used surface treatment

→ More understanding and additional shear or peel tests are needed to fully understand the active mechanisms

Strategy to identify changes in the polymer or adhesive properties:

Comparison of modified curing cycle with mechanically modified residual stresses can c.p. show if any of the relevant parameters (adhesion, polymer toughness etc.) is affected by changes in the curing cycle

In addition to post-cure straining to induce residual stresses as result of plastically deformed metal sheets

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Open for discussion

